

PRINCIPLES OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH HYPERKINETIC FORM OF DYSARTHRIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082862>

Dysarthria is a pronunciation disorder that is caused by insufficient innervation of the speech apparatus due to lesions of the posterior frontal and subcortical parts of the brain. In special medical institutions, together with speech therapists, the principles of comprehensive rehabilitation of children and adolescents with various forms of dysarthria are carried out, which includes the following:

Drug therapy for the disease that causes dysarthria;

Physiotherapeutic methods of influence;

Articulation gymnastics;

Psychotherapeutic support;

Speech therapy work.

The following types of dysarthria are distinguished:

- ❖ Bulbar – caused by local paralysis of the muscles that are involved in articulation, accompanied by difficulty swallowing;
- ❖ Cerebellar – occurs in the presence of a pathological process in the cerebellum, characterized by extended speech with constantly changing volume;
- ❖ Cortical – is a consequence of damage to the parts of the cerebral cortex that are responsible for the muscles involved in articulation, accompanied by incorrect pronunciation of syllables, but the general structure of the word is preserved by the child;
- ❖ Extrapyrimalidal (subcortical, hyperkinetic) – develops with disorders in the subcortical nodes, characterized by slurred, connected speech with a nasal tint;

- ❖ Pseudobulbar – diagnosed with central muscle paralysis, its main symptom is monotony of speech;
- ❖ Erased form – characterized by impaired pronunciation of hissing and whistling sounds.

With dysarthria, the motor skills of the articulatory apparatus are impaired. Slow, insufficiently precise movements of the tongue and lips appear. There is a disorder of chewing and swallowing. Pronunciation is impaired due to insufficiently clear articulatory motor skills. Speech is somewhat slow, and there is blurring when pronouncing sounds. The pronunciation of sounds that are difficult to articulate suffers more often: zh, sh, r, ts, ch. Voiced sounds are pronounced with insufficient participation of the voice. Soft sounds are difficult to pronounce and require adding to the main articulation the raising of the middle part of the back of the tongue to the hard palate.

Some patients with dysarthria cannot puff out their cheeks, stretch out their lips, or close them tightly. The movements of the tongue are limited, the patient cannot lift the tip of the tongue up, turn it to the right, left, or hold it in this position. The soft palate is often inactive, and the voice takes on a nasal tone.

The consequence of dysfunction of the articulatory apparatus is a severe pronunciation defect. Speech becomes slurred, slurred, and quiet. Due to the inactivity of the lips and tongue, the pronunciation of vowels becomes unclear; they are pronounced with a strong nasal exhalation.

With severe dysarthria, there is deep damage to the articular muscles and complete inactivity of the speech apparatus. Children or teenagers have no speech at all. Sometimes he makes inarticulate sounds.

Speech therapy program: Dysarthria is a pathology that requires persistent, long-term work of the speech therapist, the patient, his relatives and caregivers. A speech map of a speech therapy examination for dysarthria is drawn up. The speech therapy support program is approved after receiving a speech therapy report for dysarthria and recommendations from a neurologist who treats the disease that has caused speech impairment. Speech therapy classes for dysarthria begin as early as possible.

There are the following main areas of speech therapy work for dysarthria:

- Normalization of motor skills of the articulatory apparatus;
- Development of articulatory movements;
- Formation of the ability to voluntarily switch movable organs of articulation from one movement to another at a given pace;
- Overcoming monotony and speech tempo disturbances;

- Full development of phonemic awareness.

When carrying out correctional and speech therapy work, the following methods of speech therapy are used:

- ✓ Voice and breathing exercises;
- ✓ Active and passive articulatory gymnastics;
- ✓ Differentiated speech therapy massage (relaxing or stimulating);
- ✓ Acupressure, probe, brush, manual massage;
- ✓ Artificial local contrastotherapy (combination of exposure to low and high temperatures).

Speech therapy for dysarthria is based on compliance with the following principles:

- Systematic approach to the analysis of speech impairment;
- Stage-by-stage interconnected formation of all components of speech;
- Regulation of children's mental activity through the development of generalizing and communicative functions of speech.

In the process of systematic long-term training, a gradual normalization of the motor skills of the articulatory apparatus, the development of articulatory movements, and the formation of the ability to voluntarily switch the movable organs of articulation from one movement to another at a given pace are carried out. Monotony and disturbances in the tempo of speech are overcome, and full-fledged phonemic perception develops. This prepares the basis for the development and correction of the sound side of speech.

Tongue twisters for dysarthria are a phonetic means of developing the mobility of the articulatory apparatus. When using tongue twisters, adhere to the following recommendations:

An individual approach to the choice of means and methods of speech therapy work, as well as the principles of comprehensive rehabilitation at each stage of dysarthria treatment, allows specialists to achieve speech restoration in children and adolescents with a hyperkinetic form of dysarthria.

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